

Journal home page
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH

Evaluation of *Lepidium sativum* Mucilage as Suspending Agent in Paracetamol Suspension

Patrakar Ramling*, Patil Sachinkumar, Kamble suchita

Shree Santkrupa College of Pharmacy, Ghogaon (karad) Maharashtra, India – 415111

ARTICLE INFO

Received 23 July 2011
 Accepted 27 July 2011
 Available online 30 July 2011

Keywords:

Lepidium sativu, Mucilage
 Suspending agent
 In vitro dissolution study

ABSTRACT

Mucilages are polysaccharide complexes formed from sugar and uronic acid units. Mucilages form slimy masses in water, are typically heterogeneous in composition. The objectives of present investigation were to evaluate *Lepidium sativum* mucilage as a suspending agent, compare this with suspension prepared by using tragacanth as a suspending agent and marketed paracetamol suspension (Calpol 120 mg/ 5 ml), and study the effect of mucilage concentration on in vitro dissolution rate of paracetamol. Suspensions were prepared by using compound tragacanth powder and mucilage in different concentrations (1%, 1.5%, 2%, 2.5%, 3% w/v). Suspensions were evaluated for pH, sedimentation volume (F), redispersion, In vitro dissolution study and stability study. The dried and coarsely powdered seeds of *Lepidium Sativum* yielded high percentage (30% w/w) of dried mucilage. All formulations showed more than 80% drug release over a period of 30 minutes. The suspensions were found to be stable during the study periods. There was no any change in color, odor and taste was observed. The drug content in all the suspensions was found to be within the limit.

Corresponding author

Patrakar Ramling
 Shree Santkrupa college of pharmacy, Ghogaon
 Phone No :(02164) 257374, Fax No :(02164) 257404
 Email-rampatrar@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as: Patrakar R et al., Evaluation of *Lepidium sativum* Mucilage as Suspending Agent in Paracetamol Suspension . Indo American Journal of Pharm Research. 2011;1(3):181-186.

INTRODUCTION

Excipients are additives, used to convert active pharmaceutical ingredients into pharmaceutical dosage form suitable for administration to patients¹. Mucilages are generally normal products of metabolism, formed within the cell (intracellular formation) and/or are produced without injury to the plant². Mucilage because of its colloidal nature and viscosity can be used to suspend insoluble substances in liquid and help in preventing sedimentation³. Mucilage have many pharmaceutical application such as a tablet binders, disintegrants, emulsifiers, suspending agents, gelling agents, stabilizing agents, thickening agents. The synthetic polymers have certain disadvantages such as high cost, toxicity, environmental pollution during synthesis, non-renewable sources, side effects, less patient compliance⁴. Natural polymers like mucilages are easy to isolate, purify and are non-toxic and biocompatible. They are biodegradable and will not cause environmental pollution⁵.

Lepidium sativum is commonly known as chandrasura. This is a small, herbaceous, glabrous annual, 15-45 cm high plant cultivated as salad supplement throughout India. The seeds are reddish in color, oblong, somewhat angular and curved slightly on one side. Seeds are odorless and taste is pungent and mucilaginous⁶. *L. sativum* have been widely used to treat a number of ailments in traditional system of medicine throughout India. Preliminary phytochemical study of *L. sativum* following standard procedures showed presence of flavonoids, coumarins, glycosides, triterpenes, sterols and various imidazole alkaloids⁷. It is a well known culinary herb and the leaves are widely consumed raw in salads. The plant is known to possess varied medicinal properties. The seeds are diuretic, tonic, demulcent, aphrodisiac, carminative, galactagogue and emmenagogue⁸. It also act as rubefacient and are applied as a poultice for hurts and sprains⁹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lepidium sativum Linn. was procured from local market in the form of very small brown seeds. The seed sample had earlier been identified and authenticated by Prof B.D.Mohite, Department of Botany, Sant Gadge Maharaj science college, Karad (MH). Paracetamol was obtained as a gift sample from Cipla, Goa. All other ingredients were of analytical grade and purchased from Loba chemicals, Mumbai.

Isolation of Mucilage

The mucilage of plant *Lepidium sativum* Linn. was collected from seeds Mucilage was extracted by soaking the seeds of *Lepidium sativum* with 10 times its weight of distilled water and kept for 24 Hrs. The viscous solution obtained was passed through the muslin cloth. The mucilage was precipitated out by addition of Acetone in the ratio of 1:1 by continuous stirring. The coagulated mass was dried in oven at 40 – 45⁰c powdered by passing through sieve and stored in airtight container^{10,11}.

Phytochemical Examination

Preliminary phytochemical tests were performed to confirm the nature of mucilage obtained. The chemical tests that were conducted for the presence of Carbohydrate, Tannins, proteins, alkaloids, glycosides, mucilage, flavonoids¹².

Preparation of Paracetamol Suspensions

Paracetamol Suspensions with different concentrations of compound powder of tragacanth and mucilage were prepared as given in **table 1**. Compound tragacanth powder and mucilage in different concentrations (1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3 % w/v) and paracetamol were triturated together with Raspberry syrup to form a smooth paste. Benzoic acid solution and amaranth solution were added gradually with constant stirring and then mixed with chloroform water double strength. The volume was finally adjusted to 50 ml by distilled water. The prepared suspension was transferred into a 60 ml amber coloured bottle and then shaken vigorously for 2 min to get 125mg/ 5ml of paracetamol concentration.

Determination of the viscosity and pH of the suspensions

The viscosity as shown in and pH of each suspension was determined by Brookfield viscometer, model LVF (Brookfield Laboratories, Massachusetts) at 30 revolutions/min (Spindle #4). pH meter (Systronics Digital pH meter. Sr.No.272, μ pH system 361) respectively. pH of the phases of suspension also contributes to stability and characteristics of formulations. So pH of the different vehicles, phases of suspension ,before mixing and after mixing are monitored and recorded time to time to ensure optimum pH environment being maintained.

Table 1. Composition of different batches of Paracetamol suspension

Ingredients	Formulation codes									
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Paracetamol	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g	1.25 g
CTP	1 %	1.5 %	2 %	2.5 %	3 %					
LSM	-	-	-	-	-	1 %	1.5 %	2 %	2.5 %	3 %
Raspberry syrup	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml
Benzoic acid solution	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml
Amaranth solution	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml
chloroform	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml	20 ml
water distilled water	Quantity sufficient to make up the volume to 50 ml									

CTP-compound tragacanth powder, LSM-Lepidium Sativum mucilage

Determination of Sedimentation volume (F) and Redispersion

Each suspension (50 ml) was stored in a 50 ml measuring cylinder for 150 minutes at 35°C. At regular interval of 30 min, one tube was removed and shaken vigorously to redistribute the sediment and the presence of deposit if any was recorded. Percentage Sedimentation volume (F) was determined by using the following equation¹³.

$$F = 100 Vu/Vo$$

Where Vu is the ultimate volume of the sediment and Vo is the original volume of the suspension.

In vitro dissolution study

The dissolution studies of paracetamol suspension (120mg/ 5ml) were performed by using USP 26 type II dissolution test apparatus (Dolphin™, Mumbai, India) in 500 ml of pH 5.8 Phosphate buffer. Temperature was maintained at 37 ± 2°C and 100 rpm stirring was provided for each dissolution study. Paracetamol suspension equivalent to 5 mg were used for each dissolution study. Samples were collected periodically and replaced with a fresh dissolution medium. After filtration through Whatman filter paper 41(pore size 25 µm), concentration of paracetamol was determined spectrophotometrically at 243 nm on

UV-Visible spectrophotometer Jasco V530 (Jasco, Japan).

Stability studies

Paracetamol suspension was charged for the accelerated stability studies as per ICH guidelines (40 ± 2 °C and 75 ± 5% RH) for a period of 6 months in a stability chamber (Thermolab, Mumbai, India). The samples were placed in vials with bromobutyl rubber plugs and sealed with aluminum caps. The samples were withdrawn at 30, 60, 90 and 180 days and evaluated for the drug content and physical change.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation of Mucilage and phytochemical examination

The dried and coarsely powdered seeds of *Lepidium sativum* yielded high percentage (30% w/w) of dried mucilage. Preliminary phytochemical examination of the mucilage was given in **table 2**. It has been found to contain carbohydrates.

Determination of the viscosity and pH of the suspensions

Viscosity and pH of the prepared suspensions and marketed formulation are given in **table 3**. It has been observed that as concentration of mucilage and compound tragacanth power increases

Table 2: Phytochemical screening of mucilage *Lepidium Sativum* seeds

Sr. No.	Tests	Observation
1	Test for Carbohydrates (Molisch's test)	+
2	Test for Tannins(Ferric chloride test)	-
3	Test for proteins (Ninhydrin test)	-
4	Test for alkaloids (Wagner's test)	-
5	Test for glycosides(Keller – Killaini test)	-
6	Test for mucilage (Ruthenium red test)	+
7	Test for flavonoids (Shinoda test)	-
8	Test for reducing sugar (Felhing's test)	-

Table 3: Viscosity of suspension

Formulation code	Viscosity (cps)
F1	1.972
F2	5.70
F3	11.40
F4	15.71
F5	19.34
F6	1.10
F7	3.20
F8	8.90
F9	12.60
F10	16.30

viscosity increases but no significant change was observed in pH. Suspensions prepared from tragacanth and *Lepidium sativum* mucilage showed a pH in the range of 6.5-7.0 and marketed formulation showed 6.0-6.5.

Determination of Sedimentation Volume

Sedimentation volume of the all prepared suspensions and marketed formulation are as given in table 4. It has been observed that as concentration of mucilage and compound tragacanth power increases sedimentation volume

increases and as time increases sedimentation volume decreases. Also sedimentation volume of

Table 4: Sedimentation Volume (%) of prepared Suspensions and marketed formulation

Formulation codes	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min
F1	0.2	0.15	0.12	0.12	0.1
F2	0.2	0.19	0.18	0.18	0.18
F3	0.3	0.24	0.22	0.2	0.2
F4	0.4	0.35	0.32	0.30	0.30
F5	0.4	0.37	0.35	0.30	0.30
F6	0.90	0.85	0.81	0.8	0.8
F7	0.94	0.89	0.86	0.86	0.86
F8	0.94	0.93	0.91	0.91	0.91
F9	0.96	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.92
F10	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.96
Marketed Formulation	0.94	0.92	0.90	0.90	0.90

the suspension prepared with mucilage was found more than suspension prepared with compound tragacanth powder. It was found that, for all concentrations at the end of 150 minutes study sedimentation volume was found to be 0.1. All concentrations at the end of 150 minutes showed sedimentation volume more than 0.8. The highest concentration of mucilage showed sedimentation volume 0.98 at the end of 150 minutes study. The marketed formulation showed F value 0.94. It has indicated that rate of sedimentation in case of *lepidium sativum* mucilage is less than marketed suspension and suspensions prepared by using compound powder of tragacanth as a suspending agent. Also all suspensions were found to be redispersible, pourable irrespective of their concentration from the container. The value of F ranges between 0 and 1 and increases as the volume of suspension that occupied by the sediment increases. It is normally found that the greater the value of F, the more stable the product. When F=1, no sediment is apparent and caking is absent, and suspension is esthetically pleasing. Tingstad indicated that a flocculated suspension that settles to a level that is 90% of the initial suspension height (F=0.9) and no further is probably satisfactory.

Table 5: Drug content of formulations after stability studies

Storage condition (room temperature)	Drug Content (%)± SDof formulations					
	0.1%	0.2%	0.4%	0.6%	0.8%	Calpol
Time 0 days	99.56± 1.14	99.77± 1.34	99.19± 2.13	99.02± 2.51	99.25± 0.55	99.26± 1.34
Time 45 days	99.46± 1.34	99.67± 1.44	99.09± 2.34	98.82± 2.31	99.15± 0.48	99.05± 1.55
Time 90 days	98.26± 1.14	98.47± 1.23	98.69± 2.01	98.23± 2.11	98.65± 0.34	98.25± 0.55

Fig 1: In vitro cumulative drug release versus time profile

In vitro dissolution study

In vitro dissolution profile of all prepared suspensions and marketed formulation were shown in **figure 1**. All the formulations contained the active ingredient within the USP specified limits (within ± 10% of the label claim). Thus, all samples were found suitable for dissolution studies considering the label claim as 100% as recommended by the USP. The dissolution data for each sample was treated by converting observed drug concentration at each sampling time (5 minutes interval) and, in turn, to percents dissolved based on the labelled claim as

100%. There is no official specification for the minimum limit of dissolution of paracetamol suspensions within a specified period of time. However, the USP specifies a value of not less than 80% (Q) within 30 minutes for paracetamol tablets. In this context, the dissolution of the suspensions were found to be much faster as expected since more than 80% drug was dissolved from all the products within 30 minutes even at slow stirring speed of 25 rpm. Increase in the concentration of suspending agent (mucilage) decreased the dissolution rate as expected although the final extent of drug

dissolution was more than 80%. Investigators have suggested that retardation of drug dissolution could be due to entrapment of the drug in the polymer chain or adsorption of polymer on the drug particles. This would prevent easy access of the solvent to the drug particles. This might be possible with *Lepidium sativum* mucilage. There are some reports in which drug dissolution was somewhat enhanced at very low concentrations of hydrophilic suspending agents in presence of surfactants like polysorbate 80 (Tween 80). Others have studied the influence of particle size distribution, zeta potential, flocculation extent, complexation etc. which will subsequently affect drug dissolution. Another observation was there increased viscosity with increase in concentration of mucilage.

Stability study

The suspensions were found to be stable during the study periods. There was no any change in color, odor and taste was observed. The drug content in all the suspensions was found to be within the limit. The drug content within the formulations is shown in the **table 5**.

CONCLUSIONS

The extracted mucilage of *Lepidium sativum* has the potential as a suspending agent even at lower concentrations and can be used as a pharmaceutical adjuvant. In view of these properties, mucilage of *Lepidium sativum* can be employed as stabilizer and thickener of choice when high viscosity is desired especially in cosmetic, pharmaceutical and food industries. Quick onset of action is desired in case of immediate release suspensions. Pharmaceutical manufacturers should give due attention to dissolution characteristics of suspensions similar to those given for solid and semisolid dosage forms.

REFERENCES

1. Patel DM, Prajapati DG, Patel NM. Seed mucilage from *Ocimum americanum* as disintegrant in tablets: Separation and evaluation. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 2007; 69: 431-434.
2. Jani GK, Shah DP, Prajapati VD, Jain VC. Gums and mucilages: versatile excipients for pharmaceutical formulations. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2009; 4 (5): 309-323.

3. Odeku OA, Akinlosotu OD. A preliminary evaluation of khaya gum as an emulsifying agent. *West Africa J. Pharm.* 1997; 11(1): 30-33.
4. Young RJ, Lovell PA. Introduction to polymers, London: CRC Press; 1991: 2-20.
5. Kulkarni GT, Gowthamarajan K, Satish Kumar MN, Suresh B. Gums and mucilages: therapeutic and pharmaceutical applications. *Nat Prod Rad.* 2002; 1(3): 10-17.
6. Khory R. *Materia Medica of India and Their Therapeutics*, Delhi: Komal Prakashan; 1999: 63.
7. Patel U, Kulkarni M, Undale V, Bhosale A. Evaluation of Diuretic Activity of Aqueous and Methanol Extracts of *Lepidium sativum* Garden Cress (Cruciferae) in Rats. *Trop. J. Pharm. Res.* 2009; 8(3): 215.
8. Nadkarni KM. *The Indian Materia Medica*, Panvel: Dhootapa-peshwar Prakashan Ltd; 1954: 736-737.
9. Chopra RN, Nayar SL, Chopra LC. *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, New Delhi: Council of Scientific and Industrial Research; 1986: 845-846.
10. Baveja SK, Ranga Rao KV, Arora J. Examination of natural gums and mucilages as sustaining materials in tablet dosage forms. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.* 1988; 50: 89-92.
11. Wahi SP, Sharma VD, Jain VK. Studies on suspending property of mucilage of *Hygrophila Spinosa* T. Anders and *Hibiscus Esculentus* Linn. *Indian Drug.* 1985; 22: 500-502.
12. Khandelwal KR. *Practical Pharmacognosy, Techniques and Experiments*, New Delhi: Nirali prakashan; 2002: 149-156.
13. Martin A. *Physical Pharmacy, USA*, Baltimore: Lippincott William and Wilkins; 2001: 480-481.

